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Study on Rainfall and Temperature Trend of Khulna Division in Bangladesh

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Abstract: Climatic data collected from Bangladesh Meteorological Department was used for Khulna division of Bangladesh in this study. Three meteorological stations: Khulna, Jessore and Satkhira are considered for this study. The regression equation, the coefficient of determination, standard deviation and coefficient of variation were calculated for the analysis. Mann-Kendall test for trend and Sen's slope estimates were also calculated. In Khulna, annual Tav_g was increasing by 0.005⁰C with its average 26.37⁰C and coefficient of determination was 0.042. And annual Tav_g in Jessore was increasing by 0.013⁰C/year with its average 25.82⁰C and coefficient of determination was 0.391. On the other hand annual Tav_g in Satkhira was increasing by 0.006⁰C /year with its annual average 26.24⁰C and coefficient of determination was 0.099. In Khulna, annual Tmax was increasing by 0.008⁰C/year with 30.99⁰C and coefficient of determination was 0.080. And in Jessore, annual Tmin was increasing by 0.005⁰C/year with 21.74⁰C and coefficient of determination was 0.076. On the other hand Satkhira annual Tmax was increasing by 0.001⁰C/year with 31.32⁰C and coefficient of determination was 0.003. In Khulna, annual Tmin was increasing by 0.002⁰C/year with 21.19⁰C and coefficient of determination was 0.004. And in Jessore, annual Tmin was increasing by 0.005⁰C/year with 21.74⁰C and coefficient of determination was 0.076. On the other hand in Satkhira, annual Tmin was increasing by 0.011⁰C/year with 21.17⁰C and coefficient of determination was 0.202. Annual total rainfall in Khulna was increasing by 4.960 mm/year with its total rainfall 1630 mm and coefficient of determination was 0.050. Annual total rainfall in Jessore was increasing by 3.634 mm/year with its total rainfall 1533 mm and coefficient of determination was 0.037. Annual total rainfall in Satkhira was increasing by 1.580 mm/year with its total rainfall 1652 mm and coefficient of determination was 0.008. Man- Kendall test indicates an increasing trend in yearly. In this test the value of Z is 1.56 which is statistically not significant.

Keywords: Trend, Meteorology, Temperature, Rainfall, Mann-Kendall test.

1. Introduction

The climatic change issues have become international priorities during the last few decades. It is evident that the global mean surface air temperature has increased by 0.3⁰C to 0.6⁰C over last 100 years, with the five global average warmest years being in the 1980s (WMO, 1991, 1995). Over the same period global sea level has increased by 10-20 cm. The size of the global warming is broadly consistent with prediction models, but is also of the same magnitude as natural variability. The earth's climate is a complex system that includes the global atmosphere, world oceans, cryosphere, land surface, biosphere etc. Atmosphere is energetically the most active and most rapidly varying component of climate, while the oceans response rather slowly. It is generally agreed that the atmospheric concentrations of several greenhouse gases like CO₂, CH₄, and CFCs have increased during the last centuries. This increase is mainly due to man-made activities especially after industrial evolution. Many of these gases have long life time in the atmosphere, so that after a complete stop of man-made emissions, their concentrations would decrease only slowly, over decades to centuries, towards their pre-industrial values. Water vapour is the most important greenhouse gas. Changes in atmospheric water vapour concentration are expected to occur with a global warming; they must be considered as an internal feedback effect of the climate system, rather than an external forcing mechanism (IPCC, 1990). The current scientific consensus is that increasing atmospheric concentration of greenhouse gases should cause the world to warm. The rate of warming, however, is very uncertain. In 1990, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) estimate that with a "Business-as-usual" scenario of greenhouse gas emissions, the world should be 3.3⁰C warmer by the end of the next century, with a range of uncertainty of 2.2 to 4.9⁰C. Subsequent analysis by IPCC and others suggest somewhat lower rates of warming. Nevertheless, such rates of global temperature are greater than those which have occurred over the last 10,000 years. By the second half of the current century, the global temperature could well exceed that which has occurred over the last 150,000 years, at least. Warrick *et al.* (1994) studied the variations of temperature and rainfall over Bangladesh. In this study, mean-annual temperatures have been expressed as departures from the reference period 1951-1980. It is evident that, on this time scale, Bangladesh has been getting warmer, on average, an overall increase in temperature by 0.5⁰C which is comparable in magnitude to the observed global warming. The variation of mean annual temperature over Bangladesh follows closely to that of the Northern Hemisphere land temperature: a warming trend during 1910-1940, a slight cooling trend until the mid -1970s, and resumed warming thereafter (Folland *et al.*, 1990; 1992). For the period

1979-1991, 12 of the 13 years were warmer than the reference period. The analysis of the annual rainfall for the Bangladesh region for the period 1870-1991 showed no discernible long-term trend in mean annual rainfall. Karmakar and Nessa (1997) studied climatic change and its impacts on natural disasters and southwest-monsoon in Bangladesh and the Bay of Bengal. They found that the decadal mean annual temperature over Bangladesh have shown increasing tendency especially after 1961-1970. Recent study on Bangladesh shows that yearly average maximum and minimum temperatures has found increasing trends (Basak *et.al*, 2013) and Bangladesh is going to be one of the worst sufferers due to its disaster prone and low elevation geography (Elahi and Khan, 2015). Again, human health is at serious risk due to Greenhouse Gas emissions (Hasib and Chathoth, 2016).

.According to the Third Assessment Report of IPCC, South Asia is the most vulnerable region of the world to climate change impacts (McCarthy *et al.*, 2001). The international community also recognizes that Bangladesh ranks high in the list of most vulnerable countries on earth. Bangladesh's high vulnerability to climate change is due to a number of hydro-geological and socio-economic factors that include: (a) its geographical location in South Asia; (b) its flat deltaic topography with very low elevation; (c) its extreme climate variability that is governed by monsoon and which results in acute water distribution over space and time; (d) its high population density and poverty incidence; and (e) its majority of population being dependent on crop agriculture which is highly influenced by climate variability and change. Despite the recent strides towards achieving sustainable development, Bangladesh's potential to sustain its development is faced with significant challenges posed by climate change (Ahmed and Haque, 2002). It is therefore of utmost importance to understand its vulnerability in terms of population and sectors at risk and its potential for adaptation to climate change. In this research, variability of rainfall and temperature in Bangladesh will be studied using observational data for the period 1961-2015.

Under these circumstances a piece of research was conducted with the following objectives:

- a) To assess the climatic variability for last 56 years and
- (b) To know the trends of climatic variability in Khulna Division.

2. Methodology and Data used

The temperature and rainfalls data of all stations at Khulna division in Bangladesh over the period 1960-2015 has been used in this study. These data has been collected from Bangladesh Meteorological Department. Monthly data has been obtained from the daily data. Again, from the monthly data, seasonal mean values has been computed for the four seasons e.g. pre-monsoon (March-May), monsoon (June-September), post-monsoon (October-November) and winter (December-February). Again, yearly values have also been calculated for the above mentioned years. To analyze the changing pattern of rainfall as well as temperature, data has been plotted for monthly, seasonal and yearly basis for specific stations. The missing data has been filled up by the time mean values of the existing years. For plotting purpose, Microsoft Excel has been used. The trend of the data has also been analyses using Mann-Kendal test.

3. Result & Discussion

Using data collected from Bangladesh Meteorological Department, Average Temperature, maximum temperature, minimum temperature and total rainfall of Khulna Division are discussed in the following sub-sections.

3.1. Average Temperature in Khulna Division

The annual average temperature T_{avg} showed increasing trend in Khulna, Jessore and Satkhira over the study periods, 1960 to 2015 (Figure 1). In Khulna, annual T_{avg} was increasing by 0.005°C with its average 26.37°C and coefficient of determination was 0.042. The increasing trend of T_{avg} in Khulna is not significant. The warmest year in Khulna was 1969 where T_{avg} was 27.33°C and coldest year was 1981 where T_{avg} was 25.64°C (Figure 1). Before 2015, T_{avg} fluctuate abnormally and its cause is an unknown where standard deviation and coefficient of variation of T_{avg} in Khulna was ± 0.406 and 1.53 respectively (Table 1). Annual T_{avg} in Jessore was increasing by $0.013^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$ with its average 25.82°C and coefficient of determination was 0.391. The increasing trend of T_{avg} in Jessore was significant one. The warmest year in Jessore was 2010 where T_{avg} was 27.04°C and coldest year was 1974 where T_{avg} was 25.57°C (Figure 1). Before 2015, T_{avg} in Jessore fluctuate abnormally of an unknown cause and after that its annual variation was normal. Standard deviation and coefficient of variation of T_{avg} in Jessore was ± 0.339 and 1.29 respectively (Table 1). Annual T_{avg} in Satkhira was increasing by $0.006^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$ with its annual average 26.24°C and coefficient of determination was 0.099. The increasing trend of T_{avg} in Satkhira was not significant. The warmest year in Satkhira was 1979 where T_{avg} was 27.40°C and coldest year was 1981 where T_{avg} was 25.59°C (Figure 1). Before 2015, T_{avg} in Satkhira fluctuate abnormally of an unknown cause and after that its annual variation was normal. Standard deviation and coefficient of variation of T_{avg} in Satkhira was ± 0.339 and 1.28 respectively (Table 1).

Increasing trends of Tavg in Khulna, Satkhira was not significance while increasing trend in Jessore was significance in Khulna division. It will not fluctuate dramatically and therefore it may not hamper or negatively impact on agricultural productivity as well as human life.

Figure 1: Yearly Average Temperature of Khulna Division

Table 1: Variability of Annual Average Temperature

Station/District	Standard Deviation	Coefficient Variation
Khulna	0.406	1.53
Jessore	0.339	1.29
Satkhira	0.339	1.28
Khulna Division	0.296	1.12

3.2 Maximum Temperature in Khulna Division

The annual Tmax showed increasing trend in Khulna, Jessore and Satkhira over the study periods, 1960 to 2015 (Figure 2). In Khulna, annual Tmax was increasing by $0.008^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$ with 30.99°C and coefficient of determination was 0.080. The increasing trend of Tmax in Khulna was not significant. The warmest year in Khulna was 1969 where Tavg was 32.15°C and coldest year was 1981 where Tavg was 28.89°C (Figure 2). Before 2015, Tmax fluctuate abnormally and its cause is an unknown where standard deviation and coefficient of variation of Tmax in Khulna was ± 0.471 and 1.50 respectively (Table 2). In Jessore Tmax was increasing by $0.020^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$ with 30.97°C and coefficient of determination was 0.468. The increasing trend of Tmax in Jessore was significant. The warmest year in Jessore was 2009 where Tavg was 32.92°C and coldest year was 1981 where Tavg was 30.62°C (Figure 2). Before 2015, Tmax fluctuate abnormally and its cause is an unknown where standard deviation and coefficient of variation of Tmax in Jessore was ± 0.490 and 1.55 respectively (Table 2). In Satkhira annual Tmax was increasing by $0.001^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$ with 31.32°C and coefficient of determination was 0.003. The increasing trend of Tmax in Satkhira was not significant. The warmest year in Satkhira was 1987 where Tavg was 32.51°C and coldest year was 1981 where Tavg was 30.08°C (Figure 2). Before 2015, Tmax

Figure 2: Yearly Maximum Temperature of Khulna Division

fluctuate abnormally and its cause is an unknown where standard deviation and coefficient of variation of Tmax in Satkhira was ± 0.446 and 1.42 respectively (Table 2).

Increasing trends of Tmax in Satkhira, Khulna was not significance while increasing trend in Jessore was significance in Khulna division. It will not fluctuate dramatically and therefore it may not hamper or negatively impact on agricultural productivity as well as human life.

Table 2: Variability of Annual Average Temperature

Station/District	Standard Deviation	Coefficient Variation
Khulna	0.471	1.50
Jessore	0.490	1.55
Satkhira	0.446	1.42
Khulna Division	0.367	0.108

3.3 Minimum Temperature in Khulna Division

The annual Tmin showed increasing trend in Jessore, Khulna and Satkhira over the study periods, 1960 to 2015 (Figure 3). In Khulna, annual Tmin was increasing by $0.002^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$ with 21.74°C and coefficient of determination was 0.004 . The increasing trend of Tmin in Khulna was not significant. The warmest year in Khulna was 1979 where Tavg was 22.79°C and coldest year was 1984 where Tavg was 20.85°C (Figure 2). Before 2015, Tmin fluctuate abnormally and its cause is an unknown where standard deviation and coefficient of variation of Tmin in Khulna was ± 0.481 and 2.20 respectively (Table 3). In Jessore, annual Tmin was increasing by $0.005^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$ with 20.68°C and coefficient of determination was 0.076 . The increasing trend of Tmin in Jessore was not significant. The warmest year in Jessore was 1964 where Tavg was 21.56°C and coldest year was 1967 where Tavg was 20.17°C (Figure 2). Before 2015, Tmin fluctuate abnormally and its cause is an unknown where standard deviation and coefficient of variation of Tmin in Jessore was ± 0.319 and 1.53 respectively (Table 3). In Satkhira, annual Tmin was increasing by $0.011^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$ with 21.17°C and coefficient of determination was 0.202 . The increasing trend of Tmin in Satkhira was significant. The warmest year in Satkhira was 1979 where Tavg was 22.67°C and coldest year was 1999 where Tavg was 20.54°C (Figure 2). Before 2015, Tmin fluctuate abnormally and its cause is an unknown where standard deviation and coefficient of variation of Tmin in Satkhira was ± 0.420 and 1.95 respectively (Table 3).

Increasing trends of Tmin in Khulna, Jessore was not significance while Satkhira was significance in Khulna division. It will not fluctuate dramatically and therefore it may not hamper or negatively impact on agricultural productivity as well as human life.

Figure 3: Yearly Maximum Temperature of Khulna Division

Table 3: Variability of Annual Average Temperature

Station/District	Standard Deviation	Coefficient Variation
Khulna	0.481	2.20
Jessore	0.319	1.53
Satkhira	0.420	1.95
Khulna Division	0.321	1.50

3.4 Seasonal trends variation Temperature in Khulna division

Seasonal trends variation in Khulna division for pre-monsoon, monsoon, post monsoon and winter for the year 1960-2015 using Man- Kendall test are shown in figure (4-7). This test indicates an increasing trend in pre-monsoon, post monsoon and monsoon seasons while decreasing trends in winter season. In the pre-monsoon season the value of Z is 0.86 which is statistically not significant (Fig 4). In the monsoon season the value of Z is 6.31 which is statistically significant (Fig5). In the post monsoon season the value of Z is 2.52 which is statistically significant (Fig 6). In the winter season the value of Z is -1.36 which statistically not significant (Fig7).

Fig4: Time series and trends statistics of Temperature in pre-monsoon season (1960-2015)

Fig5: Time series and trends statistics of Temperature in monsoon season (1960-2015)

Fig6: Time series and trends statistics of Temperature in post monsoon season (1960-2015)

Fig7: Time series and trends statistics of Temperature in winter season (1960-2015)

Table (4): The significance level of the Mann-Kandell test for the post monsoon and monsoon

Season	Z test	Significance level
Post monsoon	2.52	*
Monsoon	6.31	***

3.5 Total Rainfall in Khulna Division

The annual total rainfall showed increasing trend in Khulna, Jessore and Satkhira over the study periods 1960 to 2015 in Khulna division. Annual total rainfall in Khulna was increasing by 4.960 mm/year with its total rainfall 1630 mm and coefficient of determination was 0.050(Figure8). The increasing trend of total rainfall in Khulna was not significant. Standard deviation and coefficient of variation of total rainfall in Khulna was ± 355.761 and 20.081 respectively (Table4).Annual total rainfall in Jessore was increasing by 3.634 mm/year with its total rainfall 1533 mm and coefficient of determination was 0.037 (Figure8). The increasing trend of total rainfall in Jessore was not significant. Standard deviation and coefficient of variation of total rainfall in Jessore was ± 302.706 and 18.485 respectively (Table4).Annual total rainfall in Satkhira was increasing by 1.580 mm/year with its total rainfall 1652 mm and coefficient of determination was 0.008 (Figure8). The increasing trend of total rainfall in Satkhira was not significant. Standard deviation and coefficient of variation of total rainfall in Satkhira was ± 286.309 and 16.864 respectively (Table4).

Increasing trends of annual total rainfall in Khulna, Jessore and Satkhira was not significance in Khulna division. Therefore it may not hamper or negatively impact on agricultural productivity as well as human life.

Fig8: Total Rainfall in Khulna Division

Table 4: Variability of Total Annual Rainfall

Station/District	Standard Deviation	Coefficient Variation
Khulna	± 355.761	20.081
Jessore	± 302.706	18.485
Satkhira	± 286.309	16.864
Khulna Division	± 250.936	14.741

3.6 Yearly trends variation Total Rainfall in Khulna division

TeNumber	1
Name	
Years	1960 - 2015
n	56
Test S	
Test Z	1.56
Signific.	
Q	3.06E+00
Qmin99	2.55E+00
Qmax99	9.34E+00
Qmin95	1.08E+00
Qmax95	7.72E+00
B	1.63E+03
Bmin99	1.79E+03
Bmax99	1.48E+03
Bmin95	1.75E+03
Bmax95	1.52E+03

Fig9: Time series and trends statistics of yearly (1960-2015)

Yearly trends variation in Khulna division for the year 1960-2015 using Man- Kandell test is shown in (Fig 9). This test indicates an increasing trend in yearly. In this test the value of Z is 1.56 which is statistically not significant (Fig 9).

4. Conclusion

- Annual average temperature (Tavg) in the all stations of Khulna Division was increasing. Increasing trends of Tavg in Khulna and Satkhira was not significance while increasing trend in Jessore was significance in Khulna division. Increasing trends of Tmax in Khulna and Satkhira was not significance while Jessore was significance in Khulna division. Increasing trends of Tmin in Khulna and Jessore was not significance while increasing trend in Satkhira was significance in Khulna division. It will not fluctuate dramatically and therefore it may not hamper or negatively impact on agricultural productivity as well as human life.
- Mann-Kendall test indicates an increasing trend in Pre-monsoon, Post-monsoon and Monsoon seasons while decreasing trends in winter season. In the Pre-monsoon season the value of Z is 0.86 which is statistically not significant. In the Monsoon season the value of Z is 6.31 which is statistically significant. In the Post Monsoon season the value of Z is 2.52 which is statistically significant. In the winter season the value of Z is -1.36 which statistically not significant.
- The annual total rainfall showed increasing trend in Khulna, Jessore and Satkhira in Khulna division. Annual total rainfall in Khulna was increasing by 4.960 mm/year with its total rainfall 1630 mm and coefficient of determination was 0.050. The increasing trend of total rainfall in Khulna was not significant. And annual total rainfall in Jessore was increasing by 3.634 mm/year with its total rainfall 1533 mm and coefficient of determination was 0.037. The increasing trend of total rainfall in Jessore was not significant. Annual total rainfall in Satkhira was increasing by 1.580 mm/year with its total rainfall 1652 mm and coefficient of determination was 0.008. The increasing trend of total rainfall in Satkhira was not significant. Increasing trends of annual total rainfall in Khulna, Jessore and Satkhira was not significance in Khulna division. Therefore it may not hamper or negatively impact on agricultural productivity as well as human life.
- Man- Kandell test indicates an increasing trend in yearly. In this test the value of Z is 1.56 which is statistically not significant.

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